

Lidar observations of middle atmosphere temperature variability over low latitude

M Krishnaiah & U Jaya Prakash Raju

Department of Physics, Sri Venkateswara University, Tirupati 517 502, India

and

Y Bhavani Kumar, K Raghunath, V Siva Kumar & P B Rao

National MST Radar Facility, P B No 123, Tirupati 517 502, India

and

B V Krishna Murthy, M N Sasi, K Parameswaran, K Krishna Murthy & Prabha Nair

Space Physics Laboratory, Vikram Sarabhai Space Centre, Trivandrum 695 022, India

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In this paper, 246 Rayleigh lidar observations covering the altitude range of stratosphere and mesosphere collected during the period March 1998 - December 2001 (37 months) using Indo-Japanese Lidar at National MST Radar Facility (NMRF), Gadanki (13.8°N, 79.2°E), India, are presented. The atmospheric density profiles were derived. Using the limited database, a climatological structure of temperature over a tropical site giving seasonal variations of upper stratosphere and mesospheric region is also presented. It has been observed over Gadanki, that the stratopause is quite broad and occurred in the range of 43-58 km with the temperature maximum observed in winter and equinox periods. A semi-annual variation is seen clearly around 70 km with maxima at May/June and Dec/Jan. Mesospheric temperature shows strong inversion very often. The average climatology over 37 months period is found to compare well with a reference atmosphere model (MSISE 90). The observed temperature is, in general, colder throughout the year in the 30-45 km range and warmer in summer at 70-80 km as compared to the model derived values. The present study suggests that the 45-55 km region is less affected by temperature variability, which is well suited for the detection of possible temperature trends.

Keywords: Lidar, Middle atmosphere, Temperature variability, MST radar

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1 Introduction

The temperature variability in the middle atmosphere (30-70 km) provides valuable information on the characteristics of gravity waves¹, tides² and long-term temperature trends³. In this height region, monitoring of temperature offers a valuable means to study variety of chemical and dynamical phenomena that are occurring in it. The analysis of trends in stratospheric and mesospheric temperature is one of the tools currently employed in the search for global climate changes. The largest atmospheric temperature changes due to the increase of green house gases such as of CH₄, CO₂ and CFCs are also occurring in the middle atmospheric region of 40-60 km. In fact, cooling of the order of 8-10 K is predicted in stratopause region as a consequence of a doubling in atmospheric CO₂ content⁴. Even larger coolings (12-15 K) are expected to result from steady state increases in chloro-fluoro-carbons (CFCs). These variations may be compared with the expected surface

warmings (the actual green house effect) of approximately 2 K for CO₂ and 0.04 K for CFCs (Ref. 4).

Many observations on middle atmosphere thermal structure, climatology and long term temperature trends have been made for midlatitudes by Hauchecorne *et al.*³, for the first time, using Rayleigh lidar from two nearby stations in France (OHP: 44°N, 6°E and BIS: 44°N, 1°W). They used 12 years database and found semi-annual variation in temperature near 65 km with maxima occurring just after the equinoxes. Subsequently, Gobbi *et al.*⁵ have studied the middle atmospheric temperature variability using limited database of Rayleigh lidar over Frascatti (42°N, 13°E). Recently, Namboothiri *et al.*⁶ have compared the results and concluded the fair agreement between the lidar measured temperature profiles and rocket measured profiles as well as CIRA-86 model. Chakravarthy *et al.*⁷ have studied the climatology of long period oscillations in temperature

and wind in equatorial middle atmosphere between 20 and 80 km over Thumba (8.23°N, 76.52°E). They used 18 years of rocket data and concluded that, there has not been any significant change in the pattern of temperature structure. Mohankumar *et al.*⁸ also studied long term temperature variability from the same station using 20 years of data. For tropics, using Rayleigh lidar, Jayaraman *et al.*⁹ have also reported temperature variations and comparisons with standard atmospheric model in the height range of 30-60 km. For low latitudes, Bhavani Kumar *et al.*¹⁰ have reported the sample results on temperature structure in different seasons using one year data. Parameswaran *et al.*¹¹ for the first time, constructed the temperature profiles in the height range of 4-80 km by combining MST radar and lidar derived profiles. Recently, Krishna Murthy *et al.*¹² have studied equatorial waves in temperature in the altitude range 4-70 km.

There have been a number of techniques involving space-borne and ground-based instruments for the measurement of middle atmospheric temperature structure. The Rayleigh lidar, providing continuous measurements of temperature or density with high resolutions over a height range of 30-80 km, has emerged as the most potent ground-based technique to study the structure and dynamics of the middle atmosphere^{13,14}. Rayleigh lidar will give data to an accuracy of 0.5 K at 50 km, compared to rocket measurements⁵. This paper discusses the average climatology and variability of the middle atmosphere as obtained by Rayleigh lidar at Gadanki (13.8°N, 79.2°E), India.

2 Lidar system description and data analysis

A Rayleigh-Mie lidar system was installed in March 1998 at Gadanki (13.8°N, 79.2°E), under an Indo-Japanese collaboration programme. The lidar employs the second harmonic of Nd:YAG laser at 532 nm with a pulse energy of 550 mJ and pulse repetitions rate of 20 Hz. It comprises two independent receiving subsystems—one to measure temperature using Rayleigh backscatter and the other to determine aerosol concentration using the Mie component of the backscatter. Both the receivers operate in photon counting mode with height and time resolutions of 300 m and 250 s, respectively. The Rayleigh receiver has two channels—one, a low sensitivity (10%) channel to avoid signal saturation at lower heights and the other a high sensitivity (90%) channel to cover higher heights where the signal is weak. Due to the high background sunlight during the

daytime, the temperature measurements by lidar are limited to nighttime. The method of analysis is adopted for the determination of the temperature profile from the Rayleigh lidar data of the photon count profiles, follows closely that given by Hauchecorne and Chanin¹⁴. In the height range, where the Mie contribution is negligible (35-80 km), the recorded signal intensity corrected for the range and atmospheric transmission is proportional to the molecular number density. Using the number density from the model US76 for the height of 50 km where the signal-to-noise ratio is fairly high, the constant of proportionality is evaluated and thereby the density, $\rho(Z_i)$. Taking pressure (P) at the top of the height range (80 km) from the atmospheric model, the pressure profile is computed using the measured density profile, assuming the atmosphere to be in hydrostatic equilibrium. Adopting the perfect gas law, the temperature $T(Z_i)$ is computed by using the expression given by

$$T(Z_i) = \frac{Mg(Z_i)\delta z}{R \log(1+x)} \quad \dots (1)$$

where,

$$x = \frac{\rho(Z_i)g(Z_i)\delta dz}{P(Z_i + dz/2)}$$

The statistical standard error on the temperature is given by

$$\frac{\delta T(Z_i)}{T(Z_i)} = \frac{\delta \log(1+x)}{\log(1+x)} = \frac{\delta x}{(1+x)\log(1+x)} \quad \dots (2)$$

with

$$\frac{\delta x}{x} = \frac{\delta \rho(Z_i)}{\rho(Z_i)} = \frac{\delta P(Z_i + \delta z/2)}{P(Z_i + dz/2)} \quad \dots (3)$$

where, $P(Z_i)$, $\rho(Z_i)$, $T(Z_i)$ represent air pressure, density and temperature respectively, at the altitude Z_i and M is the air mean molecular weight which is a constant. Any uncertainty in the pressure at the top of the profile would contribute to temperature uncertainty that falls rapidly with decreasing altitude.

We have collected lidar profiles containing backscattered signals, which are integrated over 5000 transmitted pulses of each scan for every 4.5 min. The

system is operated during nighttimes mostly between 1930 and 0200 hrs LT, and collected the data continuously for about 75-100 scans usually. In this analysis, scans averaged profiles are used and then a 3-point running average (900 m resolution) is applied to smoothen the height profiles.

2.1 Data analysis

Two hundred and forty six (246) temperature observations in the middle atmospheric regions were performed by the lidar system in the period of March 1998-December 2001. A summary of measurement session employed in this analysis is given in Table 1. Retrieval of temperature from raw data is done according to the method given by Chanin and Hauchecrone *et al.*¹⁴ and it is reported elsewhere¹⁰. For comparison purpose, data have also been analyzed in a similar manner to that given by Gobbi *et al.*⁵. The data analysis has been divided into two sections, namely, (i). average climatology over the 37 months period and comparison with a reference model (MSISE 90) and (ii). long-term variability, to evaluate fluctuations in middle atmosphere temperature for each month of the 37 months period.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Seasonal variations

Mass Spectrometer Incoherent Scatter Extended-1990 (MSISE-90) model, a modified version of CIRA-86, is used for comparison with the Rayleigh lidar-observed monthly mean temperature profiles. The model was run for the 15th of each month for

Table 1—Data availability during March 1998-December 2001

Month	Number of lidar observations during the year				Total
	1998	1999	2000	2001	
Jan.	--	14	--	7	21
Feb.	--	26	--	5	31
Mar.	4	11	29	9	53
Apr.	5	9	9	9	32
May	3	--	2	8	13
June	1	6	--	8	15
July	2	3	--	2	7
Aug.	2	--	--	4	6
Sep.	--	--	4	4	8
Oct.	4	1	3	4	12
Nov.	6	9	4	8	27
Dec.	4	5	5	7	21
Total	31	84	56	75	246

Note:--Indicates that the respective months are having no lidar observations due to the system problem and cloudy days over Gadanki

every year to obtain height profiles of temperature with a height resolution of 300 m over Gadanki.

The monthly mean temperature profiles computed from the data collected during March 1998-December 2001 are used to generate a colour-coded contour map depicting mean temperature variations over 4 years for the height range of 30-80 km as shown in Fig. 1. The temperatures are, in general, found to be fairly steady for the height range of 30-70 km. A semi-annual variation is seen clearly around 70 km with maxima in May/June and Dec./Jan., whereas, for midlatitudes, semi-annual oscillation is observed around 65 km at Mar./Apr. and Oct./Nov., i.e. just after the equinoxes. This climatology is compared to the model MSISE-90 temperatures, which is shown in Fig. 2. The observed temperature structure of the atmosphere is closely matching with that of the model. Tropical stratopause is clearly seen with the temperature of the order of 255-270 K at 43-58 km broadened nearly up to 15 km, and maximum temperature above 270 K is observed in this region during the months of January-May and August-October. Conversely, at mesosphere level the minimum temperature of 200-215 K is observed at 70-80 km in which the temperature below 200 K is observed in the months of March-May and August-December. The thickness of the stratopause region is found to be minimum during summer as compared to that in winter and equinoxes. Mid- and high-latitude observations are in contrast to the observed one. Hauchecorne *et al.*³ observed the maximum thickness of the stratopause region in summer rather than winter. In some days, particularly in January and February, we observed sharp increase and decrease in stratopause region in temperature profiles representing the warming and cooling effects due to the change in concentration of ozone¹⁵, besides some stratospheric inversions.

Figure 3 shows a contour plot of the differences between the temperature averages of Fig. 1 and that of the model MSISE-90. The colder regions, i.e. temperature less than the model value (up to -3 K) observed in the period of January-April and September-December between 68 and 80 km and more cooling up to -6 K is observed all the year round in the height range of 30-45 km. The temperature warmer than MSISE-90 up to 6 K is recorded in the months of April-October at 55-70 km and more (up to 12 K) in the period May-September in the height range of 70-80 km. Whereas, for midlatitudes, colder region is observed in the altitude

range of 65-80 km with more cooling of -10 K at 75 km in the months of May and November. On the contrary, warming is observed above 83 km with values as high as 18 K at 87 km in September. From Figs 1 and 3 the stratopause is found to be located at 48 km, because the observed and model temperatures profiles are in agreement satisfactorily throughout the year. According to this plot, warming is observed in

summer in the range of 55-80 km. The analysis reveals that overall a colder record is noticed at Gadanki in the height range of 30-45 km.

3.2 Average Climatology and Comparison with MSISE 90

The lidar observed monthly averaged temperature profiles are compared with similar profiles of different models in Fig. 4. The observed profiles are

Fig. 1 — Contour plot of the monthly mean average temperatures

Fig. 2 — Contour plot of the monthly temperature of MSISE-90 model

Fig. 3 — Contour plot of the differences between lidar monthly average profiles and MSISE-90 reference model atmosphere

found to differ significantly from the model in the height range of 30-50 km and 70-80 km. The observed temperature profile is found to be below by as much as 10 K compared to the models in the height range of 30-50 km for most of the months, and it is also shown in Fig. 3. The differences between the observed and model profiles are found to be much larger for the height range of 70-80 km. This deviation from model in the middle and upper mesosphere is related to the planetary wave, tidal effects and/or the mesopause thermal oscillation³. The climatology presented in this paper is obtained from several years of measurements. Of course, a non-negligible inter-annual variability may disturb the temperature field from year to year. Also the effect of volcanic eruption may have non-negligible disturbing effect. A seasonal interpretation on mesosphere region shows an interesting phenomenon of temperature inversion at 70-80 km heights. The observed inversion persists for a period of 30 min to the end of observations, which shows that this phenomenon is highly temporal¹⁶.

The mean lidar profiles for the period July-September do not appear to be so smooth as they have in the other months, because of limited observations during these months which might be due to frequent cloudy condition over Gadanki, hampering the lidar observations. In February, more cooling is observed in stratospheric region than in other months.

3.3 Long term temperature variability

The 'long term' defines 37 months record as the period of interest. A contour plot of the monthly temperature variability [$\sigma_T = \sigma_{T_m}^2 - \sigma_{s_e}^2$] is shown in Fig. 5. Here σ_{s_e} is the monthly averaged temperature statistical error and σ_{T_m} is the standard deviation of the monthly average profile. It is useful to note that up to 70 km, σ_T is $\approx \sigma_{T_m}$. The largest variability is observed above 75 km during the whole year and also between May and June, and September and October below 45 km, and also the peaks of the variability at 38 and 63 km in the period November-February, with σ_T values up to 6 K. This variability above 70 km may be due to the occurrence of mesospheric temperature inversions, which might be due to the breaking of gravity waves. The variability up to 6 K at 63 km in January is related to the occurrence of upper stratospheric warming during winter periods. The period of minimum change (variability) up to 2 K is observed between June and August below 65 km, showing an absolute minimum at 48 km and increases to above 6 K in the mesosphere. As the stratopause is the region of expected minimum temperature sensitivity to green house effects⁴, the study indicates that the 45-55 km region is well suited for the detection of atmospheric temperature trends. All trends, such as 11-year solar cycle, quasi-biannual oscillation (QBO), volcanic eruption effects, etc., may

Fig. 4 — Lidar monthly average temperature profiles for the period of March 1998-December 2001 in the range 30-80 km and comparison with MSISE-90 model and CIRA 86

Fig. 5 — Contour plot of the monthly average temperature variability

be the causes for observing this temperature variability. Further study in this respect is in progress.

4 Summary and conclusions

A 37-month climatology of the middle atmosphere temperature obtained by lidar has been discussed and compared with the MSISE-90 model data. The results reveal that warmer region up to 12 K is present in summer at 70-80 km height range and colder region up to -6 K is present throughout the year in upper stratosphere over Gadanki.

Variability of temperature evaluates the magnitude of the natural noise in the analysis of temperature trends. From the analysis of 37-month data, the temperature variability indicates that maximum variability is recorded during the whole year above 75 km and also between May and June, and September and October below 45 km, peaking between December and February. A period of minimum variability up to 2 K starts in June, and ends in August below 65 km. During this period, variability is lowest at the stratopause (48 km) and increases with altitude.

On the basis of the above analysis presented and considering results on temperature variability, the region between 45 and 55 km (i.e. including the stratopause) appears to be best suited for the monitoring and detection of atmospheric temperature trends caused by changes in concentrations of greenhouse gases.

However, mainly due to lack of sufficient middle atmospheric temperature data, the relative contribution of temperature variability is poorly defined. In this respect, both collection of temperature records for longer period and the determination of the temperature variability in the middle atmosphere are essential to study the possible trends. As continuous data for long period are not available, no trend analysis is attempted over such a short period.

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